

Preparation and characterization of novel MoS₂/ZnFe₂O₄/CdS nanocomposite catalyst for the sonocatalytic degradation of methylene blue (MB) dye from aqueous solution

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Abstract

ZnFe₂O₄/CdS nanoparticles were immobilized on the surface of MoS₂ nanoflowers (NFs) to form MoS₂/ZnFe₂O₄/CdS nanocomposite. The as-prepared MoS₂/ZnFe₂O₄/CdS nanocomposite was identified via FESEM, XRD, FTIR, EDAX, N₂-BET and VSM analyses. The N₂-BET outcome reveals that the immobilization of MoS₂ NFs could enhance the specific surface area of ZnFe₂O₄/CdS nanocomposite. Additionally, it is found that addition of MoS₂ NFs in the ZnFe₂O₄/CdS nanocomposite could enhance sonocatalytic activities in the degradation of methylene blue (MB) dye compared to ZnFe₂O₄/CdS. The scavenger experiments outcomes demonstrated that the sono-generated •OH radicals would play an important role in the degradation of MB. The degradation efficiency decreased only 5% after 4 sequential runs. Thus, MoS₂/ZnFe₂O₄/CdS nanocomposite can be used as a superior sonocatalyst for the effective removal of organic dye contaminants with high recyclability performance.

Keywords: MoS₂/ZnFe₂O₄/CdS, nanocomposite, sonocatalyst, methylene blue (MB), sonodegradation.